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“ANG SAGING NI TATAY”

(Hiligaynon)

I

Saging ni tatay perti ka bahol-bahol
Taas nga dako, tig-a kag tibsol
Panit niya daw kahoy, brawn ang kulor
Pero ang sa sulod, may puti nga sagul

II

Akon dayun ginbuklas kag ginkaptan
Pero sa kainit akon ginbuy-an
Akon nga gintayhop-tayhopan
Bago ko ini ginpanitan

III

Tapos panit akon nga ginsawsaw
Sa yahong nga may asin, katumbal kag langgaw
Tinanok nga saging ang amon pamahaw
Tungod sa saging ni tatay, gutom ko nahanaw

IV

Pero nag-abot ang panahon, ang saging ni tatay
Nagsapnot ang lasa samtang nagadugay
Kung buhi pa unta si nanay
Si tatay maka-ubra, may-ara sa amon nga magbantay

“MY FATHER’S PLANTAIN”
(English Translation)

I

My father’s plantain is very big
Tall and large in size, hard and thick
Skin is like a tree branch, its hue is brownish
But its content inside is whitish

II

And then I grabbed and hold it
But because its hot I lost my grip
Then I tried to blew it
Before I finally peeled it

III

After peeling, I dipped it deep
Into a small bowl with salt, vinegar, and chili spices
Boiled plantains are our meal for breakfast
Because of my father’s plantain, my hunger was quenched

IV

But time passed and my father’s plantain
Become ragged to swallow again and again
If my mother is still here, living
My father could get a job, someone will take good care of us siblings